

A New Method for the Characterisation and Estimation of Oils and Fats.

BY J. K. CHOWDHURY AND S. M. DAS-GUPTA.

It will generally be admitted that the present methods of fat analysis are quite unsatisfactory both for qualitative and quantitative purposes when mixtures of different oils and fats are concerned. It is thus a matter of great difficulty to detect and estimate adulterations in ghee (clarified butter fat) and other edible fats when these adulterations are made in an ingenious manner to baffle the physical and chemical tests usually employed by the analysts. Further, the usual tests are often unmethodical and extremely laborious and sometimes lead to unreliable results. Thus the colour and solubility tests used for qualitative purposes are often unreliable and misleading, though simple in nature. A rapid and reliable method for detection and estimation of oils and fats in mixtures is, therefore, a great necessity from analytical point of view. In the following investigations, a method has been developed for the characterisation of oils by subjecting them to the action of potassium permanganate under anhydrous conditions in the presence of an inert common solvent, when it has been found that the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution as well as the quantity of carbon dioxide evolved are constants for each individual oil within narrow limits and serve as a useful means not only for the detection of oils and fats in a mixture but also to get an idea of the approximate quantities present.

Oils and fats have been oxidised by several investigators by aqueous or acidic permanganate but under such conditions intimate contact of the molecules of the reagent with those of the fat cannot be expected, the latter being insoluble in water. It was therefore thought advisable to use an inert common non-aqueous solvent for

the oil as well as the oxidising agent. Such a method of oxidation has also been used by Hilditch and Lea (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3106) who used acetone as a common solvent. It was, however, found in the course of these investigations that acetone is partially oxidised when heated with powdered potassium permanganate, thus vitiating the carbon dioxide values. For similar reasons glacial acetic acid was also found to be unsuitable. Pyridine has, however, been found to be most satisfactory as experiments revealed that when heated under identical conditions pyridine (Merck) remains unchanged up to 85° while between 85° and 100° only a small amount of carbon dioxide (0.0022%) is evolved. The solubility of permanganate was also found to be greater in pyridine than in acetone. The high boiling point of pyridine was a further advantage as a solvent, for, if carried over in the baryta-tubes used for carbon dioxide determinations, it would necessarily interfere with the results obtained. For the oxidation of oils and fats, the method of Hilditch and Lea (*loc. cit.*) has generally been followed with certain modifications to suit the estimation of carbon dioxide evolved. A detailed description of the method is given in the experimental section of this paper.

Some of the applications of this method of characterisation are noted below.

(a) *Differentiation of Drying, Semi-drying and Non-drying Oils.*—It is well-known that the iodine value is quite unreliable as a test of the drying nature of an oil, for several oils with high iodine value are known to be non-drying in nature. The following method of distinguishing drying, semi-drying and non-drying oils may, therefore, be found useful.

When shaken with pyridine and powdered potassium permanganate, a drying oil (*e.g.*, linseed oil) rapidly becomes very viscous and often semi-solid, while semi-drying oils (*e.g.*, sesame oil) becomes only partly viscous and non-drying oils remain quite fluid. It may be noted that fish oils though possessing high iodine value remain quite fluid when subjected to the above tests.

(b) *Rapid Determination of Unsaturation of an Oil.*—The degree of unsaturation of an oil may also be approximately determined in a rapid manner as follows:—

When an oil is shaken with pyridine and permanganate at room temperature, it is slowly oxidised with separation of manganese

dioxide and consequent blackening of the colour. It has been found that the time required for blackening is dependent on the unsaturation of the fat, the higher the unsaturation the less the time required. An approximate idea of the unsaturation may, therefore, be obtained by comparison with standard oils of known iodine value. A preliminary determination of unsaturation in this qualitative manner, will be found useful for the accurate determination of the iodine value by standard methods as the quantity of the oil to be taken for iodine value determinations is dependent on the unsaturation and hence the previous knowledge of approximate unsaturation would be of great help.

(c) *Identification of Individual Oils in a Mixture.*—It has already been observed that when an oil is treated with pyridine and potassium permanganate, two characteristics are brought out, *viz.*, (1) temperature of carbon dioxide evolution, and (2) the quantity of carbon dioxide evolved. The former serves to detect the component oils of a mixture of the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution of an oil is not influenced by the presence of other oils, so that an oil having a lower temperature of carbon dioxide evolution behaves as if other oils were absent. When the heating is conducted slowly, the evolution of carbon dioxide for any particular oil begins at a constant temperature and if the oil is maintained at or near about that temperature, the evolution of carbon dioxide is quite exhausted after a time and no further evolution takes place on raising the temperature. This complete evolution of carbon dioxide within a narrow range (usually 5°) makes it possible to detect and estimate different oils in a mixture with the help of the characteristics referred to above.

It is, however, to be noted that the presence of free acids lower the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution while the quantity of carbon dioxide is increased. It is, therefore, necessary to know the acid value of an oil along with the carbon dioxide constants. These constants of different oils are shown in the following table with their respective acid values.

The carbon dioxide value may be defined as the amount of carbon dioxide in grams evolved per 100 grams of oil.

TABLE I.

The Carbonic Acid Constants for Different Oils.

Name of oil.	Acid value (in oleic acid %)	Temp. of CO ₂ evolution.	Oil taken in g.	CO ₂ evolution in g.	CO ₂ value.	Mean.
Ghee (1)	0.082	85	—	—	—	—
Ghee (2)	0.063	85	—	—	—	—
Cocoanut oil (1)	1.95	75	1.6336 2.0294	0.01394 0.01768	0.8532 } 0.8714 }	0.8623
Cocoanut oil (2)	2.02	75	1.2340 1.4652	0.01112 0.01354	0.9036 } 0.9214 }	0.9125
Cocoanut oil (3)	2.01	75	0.8932 1.5636	0.00544 0.01468	0.9229 } 0.9391 }	0.9310
Mohua oil	33.75	68	0.8942 1.1128	0.05040 0.06341	5.6390 } 5.6281 }	5.6310
Castor oil	2.15	80	2.1236 1.3206	0.01000 0.00627	0.4706 } 0.4746 }	0.4726
Sesame oil	0.34	65	2.4632 1.5694	0.00852 0.00549	0.3462 } 0.3500 }	0.3481
Groundnut oil (1)	5.62	65	2.7240 1.2944	0.07444 0.03512	2.7332 } 2.7154 }	2.7240
Groundnut oil (2)	5.46	65	1.8942 1.0464	0.05166 0.02834	2.7284 } 2.7080 }	2.7182
Mustard oil	7.25	69	2.3204 1.6536	0.02396 0.01602	1.0329 } 0.9691 }	1.0010
Chaulmoogra oil	14.65	50	1.8924 1.3262	0.03008 0.02191	1.5899 } 1.6532 }	1.6215
Olive oil	4.32	70	2.2234 1.9864	0.03178 0.02758	1.4330 } 1.3887 }	1.4010
Cotton seed oil	23.115	60	1.2460 1.3642	0.03750 0.04051	3.0102 } 2.9728 }	2.9915
Linseed oil	1.38	80	0.9944 2.0254	0.01482 0.03112	1.5698 } 1.5374 }	1.5536
Tallow (mutton)	3.01	80	1.2146 1.8324	0.01506 0.02290	1.2130 } 1.2470 }	1.2300
Codliver oil (Medicinal "De Jons")	0.12	62	1.4322 1.8696	0.01006 0.01305	0.7029 } 0.7213 }	0.7121
Fish oil (Rohita)	0.44	60	2.2234 1.9864	0.05036 0.04522	2.2632 } 2.2766 }	2.6299
Hydrogenated oil ("vegetable product—Denmark")	8.32	85	—	—	—	—
Lanoline	—	85	—	—	—	—

It will be evident from the data that for the same oil from different sources, both the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution and carbon dioxide value remains constant within the limits of experimental error, provided the acid value of the oil does not vary to a great extent. As has already been indicated, these constants may be utilised for the detection and estimation of adulterations in commercial fats. The usual procedure would be to remove any free acids occurring in the fat to be tested and then to subject it to the oxidising action of dry potassium permanganate in the presence of pyridine, the temperature being raised very gradually up to 85°. The lowest temperature at which carbon dioxide first appears and makes the baryta turbid, is carefully noted and the temperature maintained near about this point for some 45 minutes. When the carbon dioxide evolution is exhausted, the temperature is again raised slowly, subsequent temperatures of carbon dioxide evolution are noted and the procedure repeated. The amount of carbon dioxide evolved at each temperature is carefully determined in the usual manner. The values thus obtained lead to the detection and approximate determination of adulteration. It will be evident from the experimental portion that quite a number of artificial mixtures made in the laboratory were tested in this way, both qualitatively and quantitatively (special emphasis being given to the adulterations in ghee) and the results were found to be satisfactory. A few unknown samples were also tested with satisfactory results.

(d) *Quantitative Estimation of Oils.*—The application of carbon dioxide value for quantitative estimations of oils is particularly interesting as at present there are no methods available for the direct estimation of oils in a mixture. If the mixture consists of two known oils and the iodine values of the two components are also known, the constituents may be estimated from the iodine value of mixture. But this method fails completely when the mixture contains more than two oils or the identity and the iodine values of the constituents of the mixture are not known. In such cases, the new carbonic acid constants may be applied with satisfactory results. It, must, however, be remembered that quantitative estimation of oils can only be approximate, as the characteristics of an oil vary to a certain extent according to the source from which it is derived as well as the conditions such as soil, diet, climate, etc., under which it is formed. From the table it will be evident that

carbon dioxide values of purified oils from different sources do not vary to a great extent and hence these may be utilised to get a rough idea of the quantities of oils present in a mixture. It has, however, to be admitted that a sufficiently large number of tests with oils from widely different sources have not yet been completed.

When the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution of the constituent oils in a mixture differs by more than 10° the oils may be estimated directly from their carbon dioxide values, whatever be the number of constituents in the mixture. But when the difference is less than 10° the estimations are not sufficiently accurate as small amount of carbon dioxide emanating from an oil of higher temperature of carbon dioxide evolution contaminates the carbon dioxide value obtained at a lower temperature, though the total carbon dioxide remains unchanged. In such cases, the constituents should first be detected from the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution and when the mixture consists of two oils only, the percentage constituent oils may be determined from the carbon dioxide value of the mixture as well as those of individual oils. Still a preliminary determination of the oil having the lowest temperature of carbon dioxide evolution in the usual manner would often be found of great help ("preliminary experiment"), when it has been found that the result thus obtained is somewhat (within 8%) greater than the actual value.

When the mixture consists of three oils, whose temperatures of carbon dioxide evolution are widely different, the percentages of the constituents may be determined directly from the carbon dioxide values. In cases where the above condition is not satisfied but the constituent oils are known, the percentages may be determined from the following 3 equations, there being only 3 unknown factors:—

$$X + Y + Z = 100 \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

$$X.C + Y.C' + Z.C'' = 100C'' \dots (ii)$$

$$X.I + Y.I' + Z.I'' = 100I'' \dots (iii)$$

where X, Y, Z are the percentages of the 3 respective oils, C, C', C'' and I, I', I'' are their respective carbon dioxide and iodine values. C'' and I'' are respectively the carbon dioxide and iodine values of the mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oils and fats used in these experiments were obtained from market and were free from adulterations. These were kept in the dark and filtered before use. Oils from different sources used in these experiments are indicated by different numbers of samples. The chemicals used were extra pure Merck's reagents. In the case of pyridine, it was further purified by distillation in the laboratory.

Procedure.—1—2 G. of oil dissolved in 50 c.c. of pyridine was taken in a round-bottomed flask and an admixture of finely powdered dry potassium permanganate (0.2 to 0.4 g.) and anhydrous magnesium sulphate was added, the latter being intended to neutralise any potassium hydroxide formed during oxidation which might otherwise cause saponification of the fat. The flask was shaken for about two minutes and fitted to a reflux condenser, the upper end of which was connected to the absorption vessels containing decinormal baryta. Air freed from carbon dioxide was led into the bottom of the flask by means of a glass tube perforated at the end. This served to stir the contents as well as to drive out any initial carbon dioxide in the flask. The temperature was then raised by heating the flask in an oil bath. The carbon dioxide was estimated by means of decinormal baryta water (200 c.c.) contained in 2 conical flasks connected in series. The heating was made at the rate of 2° per minute and air was passed at the rate of about 80 bubbles per minute.

The temperature at which baryta water first turned milky was taken as the minimum temperature of carbon dioxide evolution and this temperature was kept constant for about one hour to ensure complete exhaustion of carbon dioxide, which was tested by holding a few drops of lime water at exit. Heating was then continued to a higher temperature and any subsequent evolution of carbon dioxide was observed in the same manner. The estimation of carbon dioxide made by allowing the precipitate in the baryta to settle when a measured amount of superincumbent liquid was drawn out and titrated with decinormal hydrochloric acid.

Precautions.—(1) Care should be taken that pyridine vapour might not find its way into the baryta water. For this reason, the

rate of passing air should not be too great and a long condenser should be used.

(2) In case the contents of the flask become semi-solid, as in the case with drying and semi-drying oils, these will become fluid again on warming.

Blank experiment indicated that pyridine is quite stable under the above conditions. No trace of carbon dioxide could be detected on maintaining a temperature of 85° for 40 minutes and only 0.0022 per cent. was evolved on raising the temperature to 100° in the course of some 20 minutes. As most oils and fats evolve carbon dioxide below 85° pyridine may be considered quite an inert solvent having no influence on the carbon dioxide value of the oil. The temperatures of carbon dioxide evolution and the carbon dioxide values of different individual oils have already been given in Table I.

Detection and Estimations of Oils in a Mixture Containing two or more Constituents.—The two characteristics mentioned above have been taken advantage of in identifying and estimating oils in a mixture of 2 or 3 components. As has already been pointed out, the temperature of carbon dioxide evolution serves to identify the oils while the carbon dioxide value is of great importance in estimating the oils. When the difference of temperatures of carbon dioxide evolution is more than 10° , the oils are estimated directly and in other cases recourse has to be taken to the formulae already indicated in the theoretical section. No satisfactory results can be obtained with a mixture of ghee and hydrogenated oil as in both cases evolution of carbon dioxide took place above 85° . Results obtained with different mixtures are given in Table II.

The mixtures examined in this work have been chosen arbitrarily but they are sufficiently wide to indicate the range of applicability of this test. Thus commercially important mixtures such as mustard and groundnut oils, though not examined in this paper, should evidently behave as a mixture of mustard and olive oils will do. As oils from widely different sources have not been examined, it cannot be claimed that figures given in this paper will be found accurate in all cases. The constants should be determined independently in these cases where absolutely reliable information on mixtures of oils from different sources is wanted.

TABLE II—(Contd.):

Mixture.	Percentage compo- sition of mixture.	Quantity taken.	Permanganate used.	Temp. of CO ₂ evolution.	CO ₂ value of mixture.	CO ₂ value of 1st. compo- nent.	CO ₂ value of 2nd compo- nent.	Percentages found.
Olive oil and groundnut oil.	31.8	3.8794g.	0.388g.	65°	2.2927	1.4010	2.7286	32.89
	68.2							67.11
Olive oil and sesame oil.	32.3	1.8196	0.183	65°	0.6704	1.4010	0.3481	31.4
	67.7							68.6
Olive oil and coconut oil.	59.2	4.5060	0.45	70°	1.1611	1.4010	0.9019	53.8
	40.8							46.2
Olive oil and cotton seed oil.	65.5	2.3850	0.238	60°	1.0188 (60°)	—	2.9915	65.92
	34.5							34.08

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY

Received May 4, 1931.